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Electron density measurements in low-pressure plasmas using cutoff probes and comparison with hairpin and Langmuir probes

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ABSTRACT

We present a comparative study of electron density obtained in a low-temperature plasma by the cutoff probe and compare the results with data from both the hairpin and the Langmuir probes. The measurements with different probes were conducted in a DC discharge generated by an iron hollow cathode under identical experimental conditions. This comparative analysis provides insight into the reliability and consistency of electron density measurements across different probe types in this specific experimental setup. The information acquired from the cutoff and hairpin probes enables electron density measurements within the frequency range limitations of the instruments. Measurements of electron density are performed in a mixture of argon and oxygen at a low pressure of 5 Pa, in dependence on the discharge current and Ar:O₂ mixture ratio. A qualitative discussion of the obtained results is provided.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Electron density¹ plays a pivotal role in characterizing processing plasma, exerting a significant influence on factors like deposition rate and uniformity. Consequently, the attainment of precise measurements for electron density has risen to a position of paramount importance within the plasma processing and device manufacturing industry. To comprehend electron density in low-temperature plasmas,² the utilization of precise diagnostic techniques is essential. As a response to this challenge, a broad range of diagnostic tools have been developed for application in processing plasma environments. These diagnostics tools encompass a variety of techniques for measuring electron density in plasma, ranging from electrostatic probes,³ optical emission/absorption methods,^{4,5} and laser-scattering techniques,⁶ to microwave probes.⁷ Among these, electrostatic and microwave probes, known for their simplicity in design, stand as widely adopted methods in plasma diagnostics. An electrostatic/Langmuir probe employs a slender metal tip submerged within the plasma; plasma parameters are obtained by processing its I–V characteristic.

Langmuir probe, a probe in general, operated in a flowing plasma needs an assessment as to which degree the flowing medium influences the measured data. The flow can, in principle, deform the space charge sheath around the probe and, consequently, degrade the measurement

results. The relative significance of the charge convection effect is usually measured in terms of the electric Reynolds number, $R_e S_{ci}$ (we keep the notation from Ref. 8), defined as the ratio of the timescales of charge convection by flow and that for charge relaxation by Ohmic conduction,^{8,9} namely,

$$R_e S_{ci} = \frac{u_0 L}{D_{i0}}, \quad (1)$$

where u_0 is the medium speed, L is the characteristic length (in the case of Langmuir probe, its length), and D_{i0} is the diffusion coefficient of the respective ions in the flowing gas. Using the ion mobility instead of the diffusion coefficient, we arrive at the expression

$$R_e S_{ci} = \frac{u_0 L q_0}{\mu_i k_B T_e}, \quad (2)$$

where μ_i is the mobility of the respective ions in the flowing gas, q_0 is the electronic charge, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and T_e is the electron temperature. Following, the effect of convection has to be accounted for $R_e S_{ci} \gg 1$ in the case of the “thick” sheath, i.e., for sheath thickness $\delta \gg R_p$, which is the case of our range of electron density and temperature. Substituting $L = 3 \times 10^{-3}$ m, $q_0 = 1.602 \times 10^{-19}$ C, $u_0 = 100$ m/s, $T_e = 5000$ K, $\mu_{i0} = 1.52 \times 10^{-4}$ (reduced mobility for

standard pressure and temperature), $\mu_i = \mu_{i0} 10^5 / 2$ (mobility recalculated for the pressure 2 Pa) into Eq. (2), we obtain $R_e S_{ci} = 0.092$. We can, therefore, conclude that the flow does not significantly influence our probe measurements. That is valid also for the RF probes, the surface of which is at floating potential, and, hence, they also operate with a thick sheath.

Microwave probes, including cutoff probes,¹⁰ multipole resonance probes,¹¹ and hairpin probes,¹² have attracted attention due to their uncomplicated design and rather straightforward analysis. Microwave probe methods have gained importance as a promising diagnostic technique in plasma processing due to their ability to measure electron density even in situations where the probe tip is deposited by polymers or other dielectric materials.

In recent times, noninvasive microwave probes that minimize disruptions to the plasma have been at the forefront of real-time plasma monitoring. This innovative approach has led to notable advancements in the field of microwave probes, e.g., the development of a cutoff probe. The cutoff probe (CP) measures electron density based on the transmission of minimum electromagnetic (EM) wave from the radiating antenna to the detecting antenna, and the physics behind the CP was studied.^{13,14} The plasma cutoff phenomenon was initially utilized in microwave interferometry for measuring phase shifts for determining line-integrated electron density.^{15,16} The later developed planar cutoff probe (PCP) utilizes the cutoff frequency in the transmission microwave frequency spectrum (S21).^{17–20} The authors not only proposed the planar cutoff probe¹⁸ but also developed it into a real-time monitoring instrument,²¹ with subsequent optimization and analysis.^{17–19}

The operation of the planar curling probe is based on a quarter-wave resonance (QWR) of a spiral-shaped antenna. This sophisticated probe measures the shift of QWR frequency induced by plasma in the reflection microwave frequency spectrum (S11).^{22–25} The comprehensive analysis of the curling probe^{23–25} led to its application as a real-time monitoring instrument not only for electron density but also for film thickness. Microwave cavity resonance spectroscopy (MCRS) utilizes cavity resonance frequency shift by plasma in the S11 spectrum.^{26–28} These innovations have significantly advanced the capabilities of plasma monitoring without disrupting the plasma.

Among transmission probes, the cutoff probe has garnered substantial attention in the past decade, with active investigations conducted both experimentally and theoretically.^{13–20} These studies have unveiled the significant potential of the cutoff probe as a diagnostic tool, owing to several advantages: its straightforward and robust probe system, the absence of complex equations and assumptions, its immunity to radio frequency noise and probe contamination effects, and its ability to deliver accurate electron density measurements. In recent developments, the mechanism behind the formation of the transmission microwave frequency (TMF) spectrum of the cutoff probe, often represented as the N-shape spectrum, has been elucidated through the application of a straightforward circuit model.¹³ This advancement has provided a comprehensive understanding of the cutoff probe's spectrum by relating it to the concepts well-known in circuit theory.

The hairpin probe¹² is essentially a wire shaped like a letter U. A microwave signal source is used to generate a small amplitude time-varying current through a small-diameter coupling loop positioned near the lower part of the U shape. This current is swept across a range of frequencies, causing a time-varying magnetic field to couple energy

into the structure. When the probe reaches resonance, the electric and magnetic fields of the hairpin experience a significant increase, leading to the formation of a standing wave on the hairpin. This results in maximum voltage at the open end and minimum voltage at the short-circuited end of the transmission line.

As explained earlier, the microwave cutoff probe comprises both transmitting and receiving antennas and relies on the principle of wave cutoff in an unmagnetized plasma. This leads to a distinct critical point in the wave transmission spectrum between the two antennas, facilitating electron density measurements. This article presents a detailed examination of the microwave cutoff probe's performance for electron density measurements, and a comparison with the data from the Langmuir probe²⁹ and the hairpin probe. The experiments were performed in a hollow cathode jet system with iron as the target material³⁰ operating in pure argon and an argon–oxygen mixture. We kept pressure constant at 5 Pa and changed the discharge current and argon–oxygen mixture ratio.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Figure 1 illustrates the schematic view of the DC hollow cathode jet system³⁰ employed for our plasma parameter investigations. Prior to initiating the discharge, the vacuum chamber was evacuated to reach the ultimate pressure of 2.9×10^{-4} Pa. The working gas used was a mixture of argon and oxygen, both having a purity of 99.99%. The hollow cathode is housed within a grounded ultrahigh vacuum (UHV) chamber, comprising a cylindrically shaped iron nozzle with a through-hole along the central axis. This cathode measures 29 mm in

FIG. 1. Schematic of the hollow cathode plasma jet system. Argon was injected through a hollow cathode jet, while oxygen was inlet directly into the chamber. All the probes were inserted inside the vacuum vessel perpendicular to the plasma jet at an axial distance of 6 cm from the nozzle end and 3 cm radially as shown above.

TABLE I. Dimensions of the used probes.

	Hairpin (mm)	Cutoff (mm)	Langmuir
Length	45.4	10	5 mm
Gap	1.8	2.5	
Diameter	0.8	0.55	75 μm

length, with inner and outer diameters of 5 and 8 mm, respectively. To maintain its position, the hollow cathode is secured by water-cooled copper blocks and isolated from the rest of the system using a ceramic shield. Argon gas is introduced through the hollow cathode, while oxygen is inlet directly into the chamber, as depicted in Fig. 1. Independent mass-flow controllers are employed for argon and oxygen, allowing for the adjustment of the argon–oxygen mixture ratio by setting the appropriate flow rate for each gas. The reason for creating an independent injection channel for O₂ is to have stable discharge. When O₂+Ar is injected through the same channel, the surface inside the nozzle gets oxidized, which leads to the arcing and plasma instability. The DC power supply, MDX 500 by Advanced Energy, operates in a current control mode and is applied between the hollow cathode and the grounded reactor vessel. Throughout the experiments described here, we followed the stability of the discharge by monitoring the cathode voltage and by observing the floating potential of the Langmuir probe using an oscilloscope; the cathode voltage oscillations remained within 10% of the applied cathode voltage. The nature of plasma flow was predominantly laminar, with both neutral gas and plasma exhibiting speeds of less than 100 m/s at a pressure of 5 Pa and a position 60 mm away from the nozzle end, as measured using a Pitot tube and pulsing method.³¹ Although the probes were not used simultaneously, we rigorously maintained identical experimental conditions when utilizing each probe. The Langmuir probe position and the position of the cutoff and hairpin probes were fixed as depicted in Fig. 1. The method of electron density and electron temperature calculations from Langmuir probe data were presented in Ref. 32. Figure 1 provides a visual reference for the probes' placement in relation to the hollow cathode. The Langmuir probe featured a tungsten tip with a diameter of 75 μm and a length of 5 mm.

Detailed information regarding the geometry configurations of the probes is provided in Table I, while the views of both RF probes are illustrated in Fig. 2. Both the hairpin and cutoff probes are ceramic shielded, serving the purpose of safeguarding the signal generator and the detector integrated circuit from potential damage due to discharge current.

All measurements were conducted within a DC discharge operating at a pressure of 5 Pa. We operated at two sets of experimental conditions:

- Variable discharge current from 0.1 to 0.4 A. The O₂ flow rate used was 0 and 10 sccm, while the Ar flow rate remained at 100 sccm.
- A constant discharge current of 0.15 A. The Ar flow rate used was 80–300 sccm. No oxygen was added.

III. RESONANCE SPECTRA OF HAIRPIN AND CUTOFF PROBE

A. Hairpin probe

The setup for measuring the resonance curve of the hairpin probe is illustrated in Fig. 3. A weak RF signal (−20 dBm) from the Agilent N9310A signal generator is connected to the hairpin probe via a directional coupler. This coupler directs the signal reflected from the hairpin probe to its side port, where a logarithmic RF detector, based on the Analog Devices AD8318, is linked. The coupling of the reflected signal to the side port is −10 dB, and the attenuation of the forward signal is better than −18 dB. To determine the hairpin probe's resonance curve, we incrementally change the RF generator's frequency while simultaneously recording the DC output voltage from the logarithmic detector. The corresponding reflected power is calculated from the DC voltage using the RF detector sensitivity formula. At the resonant frequency, the RF amplitude on the hairpin probe reaches its maximum, signifying that power losses are also at their peak. As the generator power remains constant, the reflected signal exhibits minimum amplitude at the resonant frequency.

1. Evaluation of electron density from the hairpin probe data

A stationary wave forms along the conductive resonator, located between its ends. When this resonator is immersed in a plasma, which behaves as a dielectric material, the working frequency f should exceed the plasma frequency f_{pl} , as expressed by the equation:

$$f > f_{pl} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{e^2 n_e}{m_e \epsilon_0}}, \quad (3)$$

where m_e , e , and ϵ_0 are the electron mass, charge, and the permittivity of free space, respectively. The resonance frequency of a quarter-wave resonator is $f_R\left(\frac{\lambda}{4}\right) = \frac{v}{4L}$, where v is the wave phase velocity. In the dielectric with the relative permittivity ϵ_r , the phase velocity is reduced to $v = c/\sqrt{\epsilon_r}$, and we have

FIG. 2. Photographs of the hairpin probe and cutoff probe.

FIG. 3. Scheme of the hairpin probe system with a signal generator. The directional coupler separates the forward signal from the signal reflected from the hairpin probe. The logarithmic detector then converts the reflected signal to a DC voltage, which is measured by the voltmeter. The red arrows indicate the direction of the signal from the signal generator and the signal reflected from the probe. The black cross on the red arrow signifies that the logarithmic detector converts the signal from the probe; the signal from the generator is attenuated.

$$f_R = \frac{c}{4L\sqrt{\epsilon_r}}$$

The plasma permittivity and conductivity are

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_0 - j\frac{\sigma}{\omega} \quad \sigma = \epsilon_0\omega_{pl}^2 \frac{1}{\nu_e + j\omega}$$

Assuming the plasma is composed of electrons in a vacuum, i.e., neglecting the electron collision frequency with respect to working frequency ω , the plasma permittivity can be simplified to

$$\epsilon_r = 1 - \frac{\omega_{pl}^2}{\omega^2} \frac{j}{\nu_e + j\omega} \approx 1 - \frac{\omega_{pl}^2}{\omega^2} = 1 - \frac{f_{pl}^2}{f^2} \quad (4)$$

Substituting the resonant frequency f_R for f and rearranging, we get

$$f_R^2 = \left(\frac{c}{4L}\right)^2 + f_{pl}^2 = f_0^2 + f_{pl}^2, \quad (5)$$

where f_0 is the vacuum resonant frequency, and the plasma frequency, f_{pl} , depends on the electron plasma density, which can be expressed as

$$n_e = \frac{4\pi^2 m_e \epsilon_0}{e^2} (f_R^2 - f_0^2). \quad (6)$$

FIG. 4. The plot of detector voltage vs frequency input for the hairpin probe. The total pressure is 5 Pa. Depicted are the spectra in the absence of oxygen and the presence of oxygen (10 sccm) while keeping the argon flow rate (100 sccm) constant. The discharge power in watts and the discharge voltage in volts are also shown corresponding to each condition. The black curve was recorded in vacuum.

2. Resonance spectra of the hairpin probe

Figure 4 illustrates a graph depicting the correlation between detector voltage and input frequency, which is also the resonant frequency where the peak maximum represents the hairpin frequency for the hairpin probe. When the probe reaches its resonance point, the maximum microwave energy is transferred into the hairpin resonator, and the reflected signal reaches a minimum. Since the detector output voltage provides a negative logarithm of its input power, the resonance is shown as maximum detector voltage. The vacuum resonance frequency of the hairpin probe has been precisely determined as 1615 MHz, as shown in Fig. 4, by a thick black curve. The presence and absence of oxygen have little effect on the probe measurements. However, there is a slight leftward shift on the frequency scale in the absence of oxygen compared to the presence of oxygen, which corresponds to a somewhat higher electron density in the presence of oxygen.

B. Cutoff probe

The setup for measuring the resonance curve of the cutoff probe is presented in Fig. 5. A weak RF signal (−20 dBm) emitted from the Agilent N9310A signal generator is connected to the transmitting antenna. The signal received by the receiving antenna is directed to the logarithmic RF detector, which is based on the Analog Devices AD8318 chip. To measure the cutoff probe’s resonance curve, we varied the RF generator frequency and recorded the DC voltage at the output of the logarithmic detector. Since this detector outputs negative logarithm of the input power, and generator power remains constant, the detector voltage corresponding to minimum transmitted signal exhibits maximum amplitude at the cutoff frequency.

1. Evaluation of electron density from the cutoff probe data

The microwave cutoff probe serves as a diagnostic method, quantifying electron density by assessing the transmission of the minimal electromagnetic wave from a radiating antenna to a detecting antenna.

FIG. 5. Schematic of the cutoff probe system. The transmitting antenna is coupled to the signal generator. The receiving antenna is connected to a logarithmic detector that converts the receiving signal to a DC voltage measured by the voltmeter. The gap between the transmitting and the receiving antenna is 2.5 mm. The length of each antenna is 10 mm.

A comparison of the minimum peak in the wave transmission spectrum measured by the cutoff probe with results from the oscillation probe revealed that this minimum peak aligns with the cutoff frequency of the plasma.¹⁵ Hence, the diagnostic method is named the cutoff probe. However, in our setup illustrated in Fig. 5, the maximum signal corresponds to the minimum electromagnetic wave amplitude received from the radiating antenna toward the detecting antenna, as will be discussed in Sec. III B 2. The relation of the cutoff frequency and electron density is given by

$$n_e = \omega_p^2 \epsilon_0 m_e / e^2. \quad (7)$$

Due to this simple equation without any specific assumptions, the cutoff method provides a rather high accuracy in the measurement of the absolute electron density at the position of the cutoff probe.

2. Resonance spectra of the cutoff probe

Figure 6 displays a graph of detector voltage against input frequency for the cutoff probe, where the peak maximum represents the minimum transmission signal. Maxima were fitted using 1st derivative, Savitzky Golay smoothing, and their positions are shown in the graph

by red points. This frequency is referred to as the cutoff frequency. Figure 6(a) illustrates a plot depicting the change of the cutoff frequency in the presence and absence of oxygen, at discharge currents 300 and 400 mA, while keeping the Ar flow at 100 sccm. Figure 6(b) shows the effect of varying the argon flow rate with no oxygen added at 150 mA discharge current. In Fig. 6(a), the presence of oxygen shifts peaks to the left compared to the absence of oxygen, which corresponds to a slight decrease in electron density in the presence of oxygen. Figure 6(b) demonstrates that increasing the argon flow rate results in peak shifts toward the right on the frequency axis, which corresponds to increasing the electron density with increasing the Ar flow rate.

IV. RESULTS

Figure 7 illustrates a plot showing the changes in frequency vs the discharge current at oxygen flow rates of 0 and 10 sccm, both for the cutoff and hairpin probes. In both cases, there is a noticeable increase in the resonance frequency as the discharge current increases. However, the plot suggests that variations in oxygen flow rates have a relatively minimal impact on the alteration of the resonant frequency.

The Langmuir probe characteristic reveals that the electron temperature decreases as the current and argon flow rate increase, as shown in Figs. 8(a) and 8(b). This suggests that higher current and more substantial argon flow have a cooling effect on the electrons in the plasma, causing a reduction in their temperature. The electron density increases with an increase in both current and argon gas flow rate cases, as shown in Figs. 8(a) and 8(b). This indicates that a higher current and a greater supply of argon lead to a higher electron concentration. Notably, there is a distinct difference in the increase in electron density when oxygen is absent compared to when there is 10 sccm of oxygen present in Fig. 8(b). The presence of oxygen appears to limit the increase in electron density. This could be due to the creation of negative oxygen ions in the discharge in the Ar/O₂ mixture, see, e.g., Ref. 33.

FIG. 6. The detector voltage against frequency for the cutoff probe. The thicker black curve represents the vacuum. Power in watts and voltage in volts are annotated for each condition. (a) A plot under two conditions: without oxygen and with the presence of oxygen (10 sccm), while keeping the argon flow rate constant at 100 sccm. (b) A plot with varying argon flow rates, maintaining the zero oxygen flow rate. The red points indicate the peak positions.

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FIG. 7. The plot of resonant frequency vs discharge current for (a) the hairpin probe and (b) the cutoff probe. The argon flow rate was 100 sccm, and the pressure was 5 Pa. We showed a plot in the absence of oxygen and the presence of oxygen (10 sccm).

In summary, the Langmuir probe characteristic data indicate that changes in current, argon flow rate, and the presence of oxygen have notable effects on both electron temperature and electron density within the plasma. Of particular significance is the distinct role of oxygen, which appears to limit the increase in electron density.

The comparison of all the probe's electron density data with the changing argon flow rate and discharge current is shown in Fig. 9. We explored the influence of all three probes on plasma density measurements as the flow rate changed. At lower flow rates, rapid changes in electron density occurred, while at higher flow rates, a continuous linear relationship between plasma density and flow rate developed. This is the reason for varying the step size when adjusting the Ar flow rate values. As can be seen for changing higher flow rates, i.e., 150 sccm,

200 sccm of the hairpin probe is not best suited as it does not show any peaks. However, Langmuir probe values are higher compared to all other probes for the case of changing argon flow rate. For the case of changing discharge current, the trend of electron density is increasing for all the probes.

V. DISCUSSIONS

We have described the fundamental properties of the hairpin and cutoff probes, along with their applications for measuring electron density. We have compared the electron density data obtained by these probes with those from Langmuir probe measurement. We have observed that the Langmuir probe yields almost systematically higher values of electron density than that from both microwave probes.

FIG. 8. Electron density n_e and electron temperature T_e as measured by Langmuir probe. (a) The Langmuir probe plot for varying argon flow rates, while (b) depicts a plot in both the absence and presence of oxygen (10 sccm). Other experimental conditions are given within the figures. The error bar for the electron density was $\pm 20\%$, and for electron temperature, the error bar is $\pm 15\%$.

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FIG. 9. The plot of electron density vs (a) changing argon flow rate without adding oxygen, (b) changing discharge current, and keeping the O_2 flow rate at 0 and 10 sccm. The error bar for Langmuir probe was $\pm 20\%$ while for cutoff and hairpin probe, it is $\pm 5\%$.

That can be attributed to the fact that both the microwave probes obtain the data from a much bigger volume compared to the Langmuir probe. Combining that with a comparatively constrained plasma stream in our system, the microwave probes average into their data also the boundary areas of our plasma flow. That consequently leads to lower measured values of the electron density by both RF probes compared to the Langmuir probe that measures plasma parameters at a position where it is located.

With all the probes, we have observed an expected increase in the electron density with increasing the discharge current and the argon gas flow. An addition of oxygen has little effect on the electron density, probably because of oxygen-negative ions creation.

We observed that the electron density in the presence of oxygen in argon is lower compared to the values in pure argon plasmas, as illustrated in Fig. 8(b). In Ar/O_2 discharges, the dissociation fraction of molecules is noted to increase with the addition of argon.³¹ The ratio of electron density in pure argon to that in the argon-oxygen mixture is 1.09 at 0.1 A, increasing to 1.64 at 0.4 A. The electron temperature remains constant after reaching 1.50 A, regardless of further changes in current values. In the case of argon with a changing flow rate, we observe a decrease in temperature and an increase in density.

Figures 9(a) and 9(b) present the main conclusion of our contribution: a comparison of all three probes for electron density measurement. In Fig. 9(a), the electron density profiles are depicted for varying argon flow rates using the Langmuir probe, cutoff probe, and hairpin probe. Notably, the hairpin probe did not measure electron density for higher flow rates. In contrast, the Langmuir probe recorded a higher electron density compared to all the probes. This discrepancy may be attributed to the size of the tip used, as the cutoff and hairpin probes have greater lengths compared to the Langmuir probe. In Fig. 9(b), the hairpin probe and cutoff probes exhibit similar density behavior. However, the Langmuir probe shows five-time increments, especially when the O_2 flow rate is 0 sccm, compared to the other probes. The factor between the electron density values estimated by the Langmuir

probe and the other probes depends on the experimental conditions. For instance, the electron density values for the Argon oxygen mixture ratio of 100:10, as measured by the Langmuir probe, are $1.49 \times 10^{16} \text{ m}^{-3}$ at a current of 0.4 A and $2.45 \times 10^{16} \text{ m}^{-3}$ for pure argon plasmas, resulting in a ratio of 1.6. For a hairpin probe ($1.07 \times 10^{16} \text{ m}^{-3}$ for 100:10 ratios and $1.067 \times 10^{16} \text{ m}^{-3}$ for pure argon), we obtain a similar ratio of approximately 1.1. Similarly, for a cutoff probe ($8.1 \times 10^{15} \text{ m}^{-3}$ for 100:10 ratios and $9.2 \times 10^{15} \text{ m}^{-3}$ for pure argon), we obtain a similar ratio of approximately 1.1. It suggests that the sensitivity of the Langmuir probe increases in reactive plasmas, especially with oxygen. This consideration is further supported by the fact that, for pure argon plasma in Fig. 9(a), the electron density values by Langmuir probe and cutoff probe have smaller differences compared to those with the oxygen presence. We have checked that the differences in geometric dimensions of both probes can partly explain the difference in the measured electron density values, and the Langmuir probe tip is much smaller than that of the other probes, as mentioned in Table I. The main reason for the observed differences in electron density values we attribute to the fact that the RF probes get their information on plasma parameters not just at the positions where they are located, but also from the peripheral regions of our plasma jet where the electron density is smaller, see, e.g., Ref. 32.

VI. CONCLUSION

A comparison of the electron density measurements by the Langmuir, hairpin, and cutoff probes showed certain advantages of the cutoff probe for both reactive and non-reactive plasmas. The cutoff probe measures plasma frequency directly, without the need of complicated formulas compared to the hairpin probe and Langmuir probe. It directly provides electron density values, as the transmission signal corresponds to changes in the plasma. Measurements are stable under boundary conditions and are non-sensitive to contamination or minor mechanical deformation. The cable's impedance is 50Ω . The measurement speed is not limited by the DC voltmeter (ESCORT 3146A),

logarithmic IC, or cables, but by the delay of the signal generator to stabilize the frequency after its change, which is approximately 100 ms. However, the presence of capacitance between the driving and sensing cables of microwave probes may affect the signal-to-noise ratio of the measured resonance curve not the value of the resonance frequency. Also, the hairpin probe has certain disadvantages. For example, the length of the probe requires an assumption about plasma homogeneity. It is also quite sensitive to the hairpin wire position with respect to the coaxial loop or symmetry inside the ceramic holder or to mechanical deformation. The classic single Langmuir probe measures with the best spatial resolution but requires measurement of the I–V characteristic and is sensitive deposited non-conducting layers.

In conclusion, our study aimed at comparing the effectiveness of Langmuir, hairpin, and cutoff probes with respect to the electron density measurement in our plasma-jet system. The results presented herein shed light on the diverse performance characteristics exhibited by each probe. While the cutoff probe demonstrated efficiency and simplicity in electron density calculations, it is essential to note that no single probe emerged from our study as being universally superior. The variations observed underscored the importance of considering specific contexts and objectives when selecting a probe for a particular application. The experimenters should weigh the strengths and limitations of each probe against the goals of their investigation. Future studies may, in more detail, further explore the factors influencing the performance of each probe. Overall, this comparative analysis serves as a valuable resource for informed decision-making in probe selection for a particular application.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Himanshu Mishra: Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Kostyantyn Tuharin:** Conceptualization (equal); Investigation (equal); Supervision (equal). **Zdeněk Turek:** Formal analysis (supporting); Investigation (supporting). **Milan Tichý:** Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (lead). **Pavel Kudrna:** Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (lead).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The datasets are available from the corresponding author upon a reasonable request.

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